

There are three species of bear native to North America. Most numerous North American bears. The most common is the American black bear, followed by the brown bear after which the polar bear. Found throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. Weighs 200 to 600 pounds. Might be darkish or light brown (cinnamon), sometimes even white. Not at all times black in coloration. 900,000 and not threatened. [we bare bears soft toy](#)

□□Location: The American black bear could be discovered throughout Canada, the USA, and Mexico. However, some subspecies such as the Louisiana black bear are protected underneath the U.S. □□ Size: Adults weigh 200 to 600 pounds and are 5 to six feet in size. □□ Features: Most black bears are black, but their fur can vary from dark brown to lighter brown (cinnamon) and even white on uncommon occasions. They have pointed ears and a straight face. Of all of the bear species black bears are some of the perfect at climbing timber. Their relatively smaller size and shorter claws make them fast and nimble to climb timber for protection, meals, and even hibernation. Nearly all of their food plan is vegetarian consisting of berries, plant shoots, and nuts. □□ Weight loss program: Their diverse weight-reduction plan gives them the flexibility to live in a big vary of habitats. In addition they eat insects, fish, and carrion. □□ Harmful? They're the almost certainly bear to be encountered in the backcountry. And sure, they love honey. The grizzly and Kodiak are the two subspecies of brown bears in North America. Most widespread bear species are found within the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Middle East. Brown bears are probably the most widespread of all bear species, found in the northern Rocky Mountains, Alaska, Asia, Europe, and the Center East. Grizzlies are responsible for nearly all bear assaults in North America, with 46 per 12 months. Though their conservation status is "least concern", their spread-out nature and diminished habitat make many of the small remaining pockets fragile. The 200,000 brown bears of the world occupy a wide variety of habitats spanning deserts, forests, and mountains. All brown bears share a large build, a dish-shaped face, and a shoulder hump. Their hair is lighter at the guidelines, which led to the identify of the most well-known subspecies, grizzly. Brown bears forage on roots, berries, insects, and fish, and a few even hunt younger mammals such as elk and moose. Their coloration varies from gentle blonde to darkish brown. The two subspecies in North America are the grizzly and Kodiak. □□Location: Grizzly bears are discovered in the northern USA, Canada, and Alaska. □□ Dimension: Adults weigh 400 to 790 pounds, are 6.5 feet lengthy, and have a shoulder height of 3.3 feet. □□ Eating regimen: Grizzlies eat berries, nuts, salmon and have been identified to prey on giant mammals. Coastal grizzlies are usually larger than those found in the Rocky Mountains on account of a richer weight loss plan. Each year there are 46 assaults and 6 deaths. □□ Dangerous? Known for his or her aggressive conduct, grizzlies are responsible for essentially the most bear attacks in North America. □□Location: Kodiak bears are only found on the Kodiak Islands, an archipelago in southwestern Alaska. □□ Size: Kodiak bears are nearly as large as polar bears, weighing 600 to 1,400 pounds, 8 toes long, and 4 toes tall at the shoulder. □□ Food plan: Their diet is much like mainland grizzly bears. Nonetheless, due to extra plentiful meals sources, the islands can assist a denser bear population. Geographic isolation from the mainland allowed the 3,500 Kodiak bears to become their very own subspecies. This has led to an extra advanced social construction which results in less conflict between bears. □□ Harmful? Like grizzlies, Kodiak bears may be aggressive. As a result of their isolation, there is just one assault on people each other yr. Largest species of bear on the planet weighing between 800 and 1,300 pounds. Food regimen is mostly made up of meat, usually from seals. □□Location: Polar bears are the most important bears and largest land carnivores on the planet. Fur seems white however is definitely clear. The world's 20,000 to 30,000 polar bears vary within the snow-covered arctic ice in Alaska, Canada, Russia, and Norway. □□ Size: Grownup polar bears are 800 to 1,300 pounds and will be 7 to 10 ft tall. They're a threatened species due to loss of habitat from local weather change. Despite their enormous size polar bears will be fast, sustaining a 6 mph tempo within the water. □□ Features: In comparison with other bears, polar bears have a slimmer body, narrow head, longer neck, and paddle-like paws. For context, swimmer Michael Phelps received Olympic gold medals with a 4.7 mph pace! □□ Weight loss program: Their diet consists largely of animals, especially seals which they will scent from a mile away. Though they seem white, their fur is definitely clear and their skin is black. □□ Harmful? Polar bears will be extraordinarily harmful. They see people as potential prey. Assaults are uncommon as a result of remote nature of their habitat. Recognized for its cream colour chest blazes. At 300 pounds one of many smaller bears. Simple to tame and sometimes common in circuses. □□Location: The Asian black bear is found in forests and shrublands across Asia from Iran to Japan. The population is estimated at 40,000 to 50,000 and is considered susceptible. □□ Dimension: One of many smaller species, adults weigh round 300 pounds and stand 47 to 75 inches tall. □□ Weight loss plan: Depending on the season it generally feeds on

small mammals, birds, fish, mollusks and carcasses or grasses, fruits, berries, seeds, insects, and honey. Assaults on people are increasing as folks encroach on their habitat. □□ Dangerous? They're certainly one of the best bears to tame (and subsequently widespread in circuses), however Asian black bears are extra aggressive than their North American counterparts. Found solely in China. 99% of its diet is bamboo. In truth, the second particular person in history to receive a facial transplant was mauled by an Asian black bear whereas protecting his sheep. Known for its iconic white face, eye patches, and striped physique. □□ Location: Pandas are discovered only in China. Only 1,500 to 2,000 stay in the wild and they are thought of a susceptible species. □□ Size: Pandas weigh round 300 pounds and could be over four feet tall, a powerful feat considering they weigh only about 3.5 ounces at delivery. It additionally has a detailed cousin, the Qinling panda which has the same pattern in gentle brown and white. □□ Weight loss plan: Unlike different bears the panda's weight loss program is homogeneous; 99% of what they eat is bamboo. □□ Options: The enormous panda is iconic for its white face, black eye patches, and striped physique. All that fibrous bamboo keeps them regular: they poop over 40 instances a day! □□ Dangerous? Attacks are uncommon however dangerous, given that pandas have certainly one of the highest chew forces of any carnivore. Smallest Bear weighing fifty five to 143 pounds. Present in South East Asia. 8 to 10-inch long tongue for slurping up insects and honey. □□ Location: The Sun bear is found in the forest and shrubland of South East Asia and India. It's the least studied bear and. Its inhabitants is uncertain however considered susceptible and on the decline due to lack of habitat and poaching. Sun bears are hunted for his or her gallbladders and other physique elements utilized in traditional medicines. □□ Size: They stand solely 39 to fifty five inches and weigh fifty five to 143 pounds making them the smallest bear. □□ Features: Sun bears have strongly curved claws, small rounded ears, and a brief snout. They are named for their pale, horseshoe-shaped chest patch that appears like a rising solar. They also eat seeds, fruit, birds, and deer. □□ Weight loss program: Sun bears tear apart trees and nests to eat ants, bees, beetles, termites, and honey. Their love of honey has given them the nickname "honey bears." In truth, they've an incredibly long tongue (8-10 inches) for slurping up insects and honey. Native to South Asia. □□ Dangerous? As a consequence of its shy nature, attacks are uncommon. Lengthy, shaggy fur and mane gave them the identify sloth bear. Sloth bears are feared by rhinos and elephants. □□ Location: The Sloth bear is found within the low elevation savanna and shrubland of India, Nepal, and Sri Lanka. With a declining population of lower than 20,000, they're thought of weak. □□ Dimension: They're 55 to 75 inches long and weigh 200 to 300 pounds. □□ Options: With their long shaggy fur and mane, they are simple to inform other than other Asiatic bears. In actuality, they're very fast and can out-gallop people. European explorers mistook them for sloths after seeing them hanging the other way up from timber. They're noisy, messy eaters tearing up termite mounds with their huge curved claws. □□ Weight loss plan: Their weight-reduction plan consists of termites, ants, and fruit. □□ Harmful? They are one of the most aggressive bears, with probably the most attacks on humans, principally attributable to surprise encounters. They blow the mud round with large puffs and suck the ants up so loudly they can be heard 600 toes away. Sloth bears stand their floor if threatened and do not combine well with rhinos and elephants, often charging at each other when in proximity. Only South American bear. World's final brief-faced bear. The identify "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that appear like glasses. This weak species of 13,000 to 18,000 remaining bears are found within the cloud forests of the Andes from Argentina to Ecuador. □□ Measurement: They are mid-sized, weighing 175 to 275 pounds, and standing forty seven to seventy nine inches tall. □□ Location: The spectacled bear is the world's final short-faced bear and the one bear native to South America. □□ Options: The title "spectacled" comes from the lighter markings around their eyes that sometimes appear like glasses. They spend most of their time in bushes the place they build nest platforms, sleep and jealously guard precious fruit and carcasses. □□ Eating regimen: Spectacled bears are principally herbivores with a eating regimen consisting of principally cactus, bromeliad, palm hearts, and fruit, however they are going to opportunistically eat mammals like rabbits and tapirs. □□ Harmful? Dwelling in distant mountains, these shy bears will be the least harmful of all bear species. Their our bodies are smaller than polar bears but bigger than grizzlies. The Grolar bear (aka Pizzly) is a rare hybrid of a polar bear and a grizzly bear that occurs in both nature and captivity. Grolar bear habits is nearer to the polar bear. They characteristic the long necks of polar bears and the shoulder humps of grizzlies. In captivity, they have been documented stomping toys, much like how polar bears break ice. Black-brown hybrid bears have been bred in captivity, notably at the London Zoo in 1859, but have not been confirmed in the wild. In 1986, a suspected grizzly-brown hybrid was shot however DNA tests had been unable to find out what kind of bear it was. Adorable koalas will not be bears, they are burly marsupials. Water bears aren't bears either, they are indestructible, microscopic animals that can survive in space. Most bear attacks happen when a bear is startled or protecting their cubs. Red pandas? They're in their very own family which are closer cousins with skunks and

raccoons than bears. 1. **BEWARE OF YOUR SURROUNDINGS.** Look ahead to bear scat and bear tracks that may indicate a bear is close by, wherein case you wish to be extra vigilant. Listed here are just a few suggestions you should utilize to stop bear encounters and keep you and your hiking buddies secure. 2. **MAKE NOISE.** This helps bears know you're here so they do not by accident startle them. Consider attaching a bear bell to your pack. 3. **KEEP YOUR DISTANCE.** While you'll have great intentions, a bear is more likely to feel threatened when it sees you approaching and defend itself. 3. **Safe YOUR SCENTED Items (AT CAMP).** If you happen to see a bear, do not attempt to method or feed it. This includes food, but additionally your toiletries, for example. Whichever technique you select, ensure it's at the very least 200 feet away from your tent so you don't attract bears to your campsite. 4. **Stay CALM.** For those who meet a bear, do not run. Try to make yourself look as huge as potential, waving your arms above your head. You may also lengthen a jacket above your head to make your self look larger. Lock these things in a bear canister or use a bear bag to hold them up in a tree. Don't scream or attempt to scare the bear. 5. **USE BEAR SPRAY (AS A last RESORT).** Converse to it calmly and slowly again away. Full instruction on how to make use of bear spray here. If the bear is dangerously shut (30 ft) or is charging at you, pull out your bear spray and use it in 1-2 second bursts, aiming barely downward. 6. **Battle Again.** If all else fails and a bear assaults you, do not play lifeless. Which bear is the biggest? Averaging 900-1500 lbs, 8.0 to 8.4 feet lengthy, and 4.0 to 5.25 ft tall, the most important bear by both size and weight is the polar bear. The largest ever recorded was 2,200 lbs. Fight again with all of your energy and hope that it'll back down. Which bear is the most dangerous? All bears are harmful if provoked. Globally, the Asian black bear is understood for essentially the most assaults. When in bear nation, it's at all times wise to hold bear spray. It's nicely deserved, particularly when cubs are round. Annually there are approximately 46 grizzly attacks, 6 resulting in demise. In North America, grizzly bears have probably the most fearsome fame. Which bear is the strongest? Whereas you're most more likely to see an American black bear, on common there is just one attack per yr. By way of raw chew energy, measured in Newtons, the polar bear's chunk reigns supreme. All bears are robust and not to be messed with. When using the chunk drive quotient (chunk energy relative to dimension), the sun bear packs the most punch. Initially named "Hotfoot Teddy", Smokey Bear was a black bear cub discovered within the spring of 1950 after a wildfire in New Mexico. He had climbed a tree to escape the fireplace however sustained burns on his paws and hind legs. Quickly after he became an icon and to at the present time is the star of the longest-operating public service announcement campaign. Yogi Bear is an animated bear known for his love of "pic-a-nic" baskets. Extra importantly Yogi Bear has inspired countless thru-hikers to attempt to grasp the art of "yogi-ing", the act of not quite begging however receiving favors from strangers. Baloo s a sloth bear, though he has some traits of the Asian black bear. He's an easygoing, pleasant bear who lives a duty-free lifestyle. He also is perhaps the primary bear to obtain his pilot's license. Earlier than he was the storybook teddy bear, Winnie the Pooh was a black bear from Canada which the author's son usually would visit at the London Zoo. Winnie is brief for "Winnipeg," the city in Canada close to the place he was from. Chris additionally wrote How you can Hike the Appalachian Trail. Equal parts backpacking food and ultralight gear. After via-hiking the Appalachian Path, Chris Cage created Greenbelly to provide fast, filling and balanced meals to backpackers. Get epic ideas, guides and how-to's in your inbox every two weeks.

